

Synthesis of Some New N-Heterocyclic Disperse Dyes

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Some new N-heterocyclic disperse dyes have been synthesised and their application to polyester (PES) and polyamide (PA) fibres has been studied.

AZO coupling products of some pyridin-2,6-diones are reported as excellent disperse dyes for polyester fibre¹⁻³. These observations prompted us, designing a new class of N-heterocyclic disperse dyes and a study of their application to polyester (PES) and polyamide (PA) fibres.

Condensation of 3-(2'-methyl-4'-methoxy/ethoxy-5'-isopropyl phenyl) glutamic acid (1), with primary aromatic amines furnished the desired piperidinediones (2), (3) and (4) [Scheme 1].

SCHEME - 1

(1)

R = -OCH₃; -OC₂H₅; 1. R' = -H; -Cl 2. R = -OCH₃; R' = -H
3. R = -OC₂H₅; R' = -H
4. R = -OCH₃; R' = -Cl

(i) ArN⁺₂Cl⁻; (ii) 0 to -5°C
↓ (iii) NaOH; (iv) pH 7.0 to 7.5

(2a to 1; 3a to 1; 4a to 1)

2. R = -OCH₃; 3. R = -OC₂H₅; R' = -H
4. R = -OCH₃; R' = -Cl
R'' for 2a to 1; 3a to 1; 4a to 1 = -H; -2-Cl; -3-Cl; -4-Cl;
-2-NO₂; -3-NO₂; -4-NO₂;
-2-OH₂; -3-OH₂; -4-OH₂;
-2-OCH₃; 4-OCH₃

These piperidinediones when coupled with different benzenediazonium salts yielded the desired disperse dyes. The structure of these dyes and that of the intermediates have been established beyond any doubts⁴. In our earlier publication⁴, we have reported the synthesis and structure elucidation of compounds (2) and 2a to 2l. In this publication, we would like to communicate the synthesis of some more similar compounds viz. (3), (3a to 3l) and (4), (4a to 4l).

These dyes were tested on polyester (PES) and polyamide (PA) fibres. The standard dyeing procedures were adopted using 2% shade.

Experimental

1-Phenyl-4-(2'-methyl-4'-ethoxy-5'-isopropyl phenyl)-3-ene-2, 6-piperidine dione (3).

3-2(2'-methyl-4'-ethoxy-5'-isopropyl phenyl) glutamic acid⁵ 1.53 g (0.005 mole) was condensed with freshly distilled aniline 0.45 ml (0.005 mole) under reflux for ½ hour. A sticky mass thus obtained was washed several times with dil. HCl and crystallised from ethanol to obtain colourless crystals of (3). Comp. (3) m.p. 216-217°.

Found: C, 76.00; H, 6.89; N, 3.63%. Calculated for C₂₃H₂₅O₃N, C, 76.02; H, 6.93; N, 3.86%.

1-phenyl-4-(2'-methyl-4'-ethoxy-5'-isopropyl phenyl)-3-ene-2, 6-piperidine dione-5-phenyl-hydrazone (3a):

Compound (3) 0.362 g (0.001 mole) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide sodium acetate buffer (pH 7.00 to 7.50) and the resulting solution was chilled to 0° and treated with a cooled and clear solution of benzenediazonium chloride (prepared by diazotizing aniline 0.1 ml (0.001 mole) dissolved in 1.0 ml of 2N HCl with 0.001 mole of NaNO₂ in 5.0 ml of water) with constant stirring. The coloured product was filtered, washed three to four times with water and crystallised from ethanol to get needles of 3a m.p. 156-158°. Comp. 3a Found C, 74.47; H, 6.22, N, 8.84%. Calculated for C₂₉H₂₉O₃N₃ C, 74.50; H, 6.25, N, 8.99%.

Compounds 3b to 3l and 4a to 4l were prepared adopting the above procedure.

For the light fastness grading, these dyeings were exposed for 100 hrs in sunlight and to establish their sublimation fastness they were subjected to BA F precision press for 30 seconds at 180°. The washing fastness test was carried out in a Laurometer (AATCC) SNV₄ using 5g/lit soap and 2.0 g/lit.

TABLE 1

No.	R'	Molecular formula	Carbon%		Hydrogen%		Nitrogen%		M.P. °C	Yield%
			Found	Actual	Found	Actual	Found	Actual		
3	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₂ N	76.00	76.02	6.89	6.98	3.63	3.86	216-217	69
4	-2-Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₂ NCl	68.77	68.84	5.76	5.78	9.07	9.24	233	57

TABLE 2a—SERIES II

No.	R'	Molecular formula	Carbon%		Hydrogen%		Nitrogen%		M.P. °C	Colour	Yield%	UV in MeOH	
			Found	Actual	Found	Actual	Found	Actual				UV cm ⁻¹	Visible cm ⁻¹
3a	H	C ₂₉ H ₃₉ O ₂ N ₂	74.47	74.50	6.22	6.25	8.84	8.99	156-158	Dark Brown	69	254	416
3b	-2-Cl	C ₂₉ H ₃₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	69.34	69.37	5.60	5.62	8.17	8.37	140-141	Dark Brown	67	257	419
3c	-3-Cl	C ₂₉ H ₃₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	69.30	69.37	5.62	5.62	8.19	8.37	181-182	Yellowish orange	54	259	410
3d	-4-Cl	C ₂₉ H ₃₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	69.28	69.37	5.67	5.62	8.19	8.37	151-152	—	59	257	410
3e	-2-NO ₂	C ₂₉ H ₃₅ O ₂ N ₄	67.94	67.98	5.48	5.51	10.72	10.93	190-191	Greenish yellow	66	262	428
3f	-3-NO ₂	C ₂₉ H ₃₅ O ₂ N ₄	67.90	67.98	5.49	5.51	10.81	10.93	190-191	Green	66	262	418
3g	-4-NO ₂	C ₂₉ H ₃₅ O ₂ N ₄	67.96	67.98	5.45	5.51	10.77	10.93	159-160	Green	59	257	421
3h	-2-CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₄₁ O ₂ N ₂	74.80	74.84	6.49	6.49	8.70	8.73	128-130	Brown	72	267	425
3i	-3-CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₄₁ O ₂ N ₂	74.86	74.84	6.35	6.49	8.63	8.73	122-123	Yellowish green	65	261	425
3j	-4-CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₄₁ O ₂ N ₂	74.89	74.84	6.62	6.49	8.69	8.73	161-162	Darkred	70	260	428
3k	-2-OCH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₄₁ O ₂ N ₂	72.39	72.41	6.24	6.28	8.24	8.44	181-182	Darkbrown	51	264	430
3l	-4-OCH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₄₁ O ₂ N ₂	72.37	72.41	6.24	6.28	8.31	8.44	223-225	Reddish Brown	48	265	428

soda solution with M : L ratio 1 : 50. Ten steel balls were introduced into the pot. The test was carried out at 95 ± 2° for 30 minutes. The pick-up values of these dyes have been obtained by comparing these dyes with standard shade cards.

Results and Discussion

(1) *Light Fastness*: The light fastness of the dyes obtained in the present project was found to be satisfactory (Table 4) ranging from fair to good on polyesters, however, poor light fastness was observed on polyamide fibres. Series III dyes (Table 3c) showed better results than series I⁴ and II (Table 2⁴ and 2a). In series III, the dyes contain in addition

to groups -OCH₃, -NO₂, -Cl, another -Cl atom. The better light fastness displayed by this series may be attributed to the presence of additional -Cl atom, as halogens are known to enhance the colouristic property of the dyes. The bathochromic effect of the ortho -Cl atom is characteristic and significant. The difference in shade and light fastness observed on PES and PA fibres in these series of dyes is probably related to the effect of the dye molecule on the strength of the force which attract the dye to active sites in the fibre. Compounds (2e, 3e and 4e), showed better light fastness presumably due to hydrogen bonding in the ortho nitro hydrazone structure.

TABLE 3—(SERIES III)

No.	R''	Molecular formula	Carbon%		Hydrogen%		Nitrogen%		M.P.°C	Yield%	Colour	Ultraviolet	
			Found	Actual	Found	Actual	Found	Actual				UV cm ⁻¹	Visible cm ⁻¹
4a	-H	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	68.90	68.93	5.81	5.37	8.51	8.61	160-161	72	Brown	250	413
4b	-2-Cl	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	64.30	64.37	4.81	4.82	8.00	8.04	155-156	84	Brown	254	410
4c	-3-Cl	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	64.25	64.37	4.80	4.82	7.87	8.04	173-175	65	Pale orange	256	407
4d	-4-Cl	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	64.29	64.37	4.77	4.82	7.87	8.04	161-163	67	Bright yellow	249	411
4e	-2-NO ₂	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	63.03	63.10	4.71	4.73	10.35	10.52	185-187	73	Greenish yellow	259	420
4f	-3-NO ₂	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	63.07	63.10	4.77	4.73	10.31	10.52	155-157	68	Yellow	260	416
4g	-4-NO ₂	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	63.04	63.10	4.71	4.73	10.39	10.52	203-204	67	Reddish brown	254	429
4h	-2-CH ₃	C ₂₉ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	69.34	69.38	5.60	5.62	8.17	8.37	235-237	64	Dark brown	261	422
4i	-3-CH ₃	C ₂₉ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	69.37	69.38	5.58	5.62	8.11	8.37	193-200	60	Light brown	260	420
4j	-4-CH ₃	C ₂₉ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	69.33	69.38	5.56	5.62	8.12	8.37	217-219	52	Orange	259	425
4k	-2-OCH ₃	C ₂₉ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	67.17	67.23	5.40	5.45	8.01	8.11	177-179	57	Brick red	260	427
4l	-4-OCH ₃	C ₂₉ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	67.14	67.23	5.39	5.45	7.96	8.11	211-213	61	Bright yellow	262	428

Sublimation fastness :

Sublimation fastness is dependant on vapour pressure of a dye. It has been observed that the vapour pressure of a dye is inversely proportional to its mass and polarity⁶. Based on these observations the dyes under consideration particularly of series-III, containing polar -Cl atom and having higher molecular weight as compared to series-I⁴ and II showed good sublimation fastness ranging from fair to excellent (Table 4).

Washing fastness :

In case of polyester and other synthetic fibres having more compact structures, dyeing is done at 110° to 120°, whereas washing is done at relatively lower temperature, the desorption of the dye is much less. Increase in molecular weight enhances wash fastness⁷. Washing fastness of these dyes (Table 4) varied from fair to good. In general, the molecular complexity of these dyes helped to achieve better wash fastness for all the three series.

TABLE 4

Test		Series-I	Series-II	Series-III
Xeno	PES	4-5	3-4	3-4
	PA	4+	2-3+	2-3+
Thermo	PES	4-5	3-4	3-4
	PA	—	—	—
Washing	PES	3-4	3-4	3-4
	PA	—	—	—

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